

Report on assessment framework on gender-based violence in RPOs

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Assessment framework to take stock, measure progresses, and identify strengths and weakness in organisational responses to gender-based violence along the 7Ps

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¹ This document will be a draft until it is approved by the coordinator.

² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Partners

SUMMARY

This deliverable presents an assessment framework to support universities and research organisations in their work against gender-based violence. It is based in the logic of the Impact Driver Model (Mergaert et al. 2022) and draws on the knowledge produced throughout the UniSAFE project. The objective is to develop an assessment framework to enable the identification of the strengths and weaknesses of universities and research organisations, and to assess progress, in addressing gender-based violence. It is informed by the micro, meso and macro level research conducted in UniSAFE WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and the consortium and stakeholder workshops in WP5, WP6, and WP7. The assessment framework is presented as tool to be used by individual universities and research organisations, and includes the 7P model (Prevalence, Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of Services, Partnerships and Policy).

It builds upon the ideas and concepts established in the Impact Driver Model on gender equality and provides specific indicators that can be used by RPOs to assess their overall institutional capacity and progress on addressing gender-based violence. The assessment framework consists of eight impact drivers and 18 indicators, and seven sub-indicators detailing each P of the 7P model. The impact drivers include institutional frameworks, concepts, institutional measures, victim-centred approach, knowledge and expertise, leadership commitment, information and communication, and monitoring and evaluation.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Associated Countries
CoE	Council of Europe
EC	European Commission
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
ID	Impact Driver
IDM	Impact Driver Model
MS	Member States
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SH	Sexual Harassment
UN	United Nations
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
WP	Work Package

ABOUT UNISAFE

UniSAFE is a Horizon 2020 project (grant agreement number 101006261) funded under the call topic *SwafS-25-2020: Gender-based violence including sexual harassment in research organisations and universities*. It has a dual objective: (1) to produce robust knowledge on gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in universities and research organisations and (2) to translate the knowledge into operational tools and recommendations for universities, research organisations, and policy stakeholders to reduce gender-based violence.

In analysing the mechanisms of gender-based violence and its social determinants and consequences, UniSAFE is centred on three research pillars that are combined in a holistic research model (Strid et al. 2021).

1. The first one, at the micro level, is the study of the **prevalence and consequences of gender-based violence** through a survey in 46 institutions, and individual interviews with researchers at increased risk of gender-based violence.
2. The second one, at the meso level, is a study of **organisational infrastructure and responses** that are analysed through in-depth case studies, and a strategic mapping of research organisations in 15 EU countries.
3. The third one, at the macro level, is an analysis of **legal and policy frameworks** focused specifically on gender-based violence in universities and research organisations, conducted in cooperation with national experts in 27 EU member states (MS), four Associated Countries (AC), and two Third Countries.

INTRODUCTION

In UniSAFE, the task T6.3 *Development of the assessment framework on gender-based violence in RPOs* aims to use the results produced throughout the project to provide an assessment framework for assessing RPO's overall institutional capacity and progress on addressing gender-based violence.

This deliverable presents this assessment framework. It is informed by the micro-, meso and macro level research conducted in UniSAFE WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and the consortium and stakeholder workshops in WP7. The assessment framework is presented as an overall self-assessment framework to be used by individual RPOs and includes the 7P model (Prevalence, Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of Services, Partnerships and Policy).

This assessment framework builds upon the ideas and concepts established in the Impact Driver Model on gender equality (Mergaert et al. 2022) and provides specific indicators that can be used by RPOs to assess their overall institutional capacity and progress on

addressing gender-based violence. The assessment framework consists in total of eight impact drivers and 18 indicators, and seven sub-indicators detailing each P of the 7P model, which are described in turn. This is followed by guidance on how to obtain a score that summarises their progress. The operational assessment framework is presented further down.

METHODOLOGY

The assessment framework was developed as a collaborative effort of the UniSAFE project; it is based on the work carried out throughout the WPs and builds on the experience and knowledge gained from all WPs. It is further based on existing experiences and knowledge from other EU-funded projects, such as the LIBRA, Gender-SMART and CASPER projects).³ The Impact Driver Model (Mergaert et al. 2022) was used as a key framework to guide its development, as it aims to complement it for RPOs that specifically want to address gender-based violence.

The first step towards developing this assessment framework and the selection of impact drivers and indicators was taken in the UniSAFE state of the art theoretical and conceptual framework, which identified key issues and challenges in addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations, defined the forms of gender-based violence and intersectionality, and contextualised the 7P framework to the setting of higher education and research institutions (Strid et al. 2021).

The second step was the implementation of the theoretical and conceptual framework throughout the research WPs and fieldwork in UniSAFE (WP3, WP4, WP5), and the analysis of the prevalence, causes and consequences of gender-based violence in RPOs, the analysis of researchers at increased risk of gender-based violence, the analysis of the national and institutional policies addressing gender-based violence, as well as the analysis of institutional measures to address gender-based violence (Blazyte & Pilinkaite Sotirovic 2023; Fajmonová et al. 2021; Huck et al. 2022; Lipinsky et al. 2022; Ranea-Triviño et al. 2000).

The third step was taken co-jointly with the start of WP6, where the results from previous WPs were integrated into a multilevel dataset and analysis, which included the identification of indicators to analyse the prevalence, causes and consequences of gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations (Humbert et al. 2022). This identification of indicators served as a starting point for the first draft of the assessment framework.

Fourth, a first full draft was developed, presented and shared with the consortium. This draft was discussed and further developed at a partner workshop at the Institute for Sociology at the Czech Academy of Sciences in Prague in November 2022.

³ LIBRA (contract no 665937), Gender-SMART (contract no 824546) and CASPER (contract no. 872113).

All in all, the model was discussed by the UniSAFE partners in three workshops, held respectively in Oxford (June 2022), in Oxford on (September 2022) and Prague in (November 2022). The first two discussed indicators, whereas the third worked on the structure and rubrics. Thereafter the framework was re-drafted in three rounds, each incorporating and considering the results of the WP7 workshops carried out with consortium partners, academic experts and practitioners in spring 2023. Finally, the framework, its impact drivers, indicators and rubrics were revised, and a fourth final version was produced and finalised after being reviewed by the quality reviewers and the consortium.

Limitations of the approach:

- The impact drivers reflect prerequisites for an effective approach to addressing gender-based violence, with the rubrics detailing specific requirements for each of the impact drivers' indicators. This representation is the result of choices made by the authors. While some elements were elevated to the status of 'impact driver' (e.g., a victim-centred approach), others were more mainstreamed into the rubrics (e.g. availability of resources). These decisions have been extensively discussed in the team, but also imply a somewhat simplified representation of requirements.
- The authors decided to present each P of the 7P model as a stand-alone indicator. Consequently, the rubrics for each P contain a limited number of requirements. Other requirements that are of a more cross-cutting nature, and apply for all Ps, have been put forward as stand-alone impact drivers and were positioned before the series of Ps.

SELECTED IMPACT DRIVERS

1. **Institutional frameworks:** This impact driver covers policies, responsible management roles, experts on gender-based violence, budget frame, and other necessary measures for institutional change. Institutional frameworks refer to Institutional framework refers to a holistic policy approach, an overarching system, going beyond single policy (documents) addressing gender-based violence.
2. **Concepts:** This impact driver covers the coverage and definition of multiple forms of gender-based violence and their inclusion in policies and measures, and intersectionality and the extent to which multiple inequalities and inequality groups are addressed in policy and measures.
3. **Victim-centred approach:** This impact driver covers the institutions' awareness and consideration of the experiences and needs of victims and potential victims.
4. **Knowledge and expertise:** This impact driver covers available knowledge and expertise, and the use thereof, in policy design, implementation, evaluation, capacity-building initiatives, and support material to address gender-based violence.

5. **Leadership commitment:** This impact driver covers the proactive engagement on all levels of management in an institution to support various measures of institutional responses to gender-based violence.
6. **Information and communication.** This impact driver covers transparent and systemic dissemination of policy, data, measures, knowledge and support structure for all target groups.
7. **Monitoring and evaluation.** This impact driver covers the necessary protocol or procedure to systematically identify the progress of institutional measures to address gender-based violence, and to improve them. It captures the need for institutional learning.
8. **Institutional measures:** This impact driver covers the comprehensiveness of the 7P model and consists of a set of seven sub-indicators on policy, prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and partnerships. In this impact driver, the p for policy refers to policy documents.

IMPACT DRIVERS AND INDICATORS

The assessment framework consists of eight impact drivers that sum up necessary preconditions for addressing gender-based violence in RPOs (see Table 1). These impact drivers can be understood as the necessary components for RPOs to put in place to effectively address gender-based violence. Each impact driver, and associated indicators are described below, together with an examination of their relevance to enable RPOs to address gender-based violence.

Table 1: Impact drivers and indicators for addressing gender-based violence in RPOs

Impact driver	Indicators			
ID1: Institutional framework	INDICATOR A: Institutional framework for addressing GBV			
ID2: Concepts Coverage and knowledge of the forms of GBV and their intersections	INDICATOR A: Coverage and definitions of the forms of GBV	INDICATOR B: Intersectionality		
ID3: Victim centred approach for addressing GBV	INDICATOR A: Victim centred approach			
ID4: Available competencies, capacity-building initiatives, and support material	INDICATOR A: Knowledge and internal expertise on GBV	INDICATOR B: Capacity-building initiatives on addressing GBV	INDICATOR C: Provision of support materials for GBV	
ID5: Leadership commitment	INDICATOR A: Leadership commitment			
ID6: Transparency of policies, data, measures, knowledge and support structures	INDICATOR A: Internal transparency of policy, data, measures, knowledge, and support structures	INDICATOR B: External transparency of policy, data, measures, knowledge, and support structures		
ID7: Existence of structures and incentives for monitoring and evaluation	INDICATOR A: Existence of structures or other incentives for monitoring and evaluation of measures to address GBV			
ID8: Institutional measures: Coverage and use of the 7P model	INDICATOR A: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prevalence)	INDICATOR B: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prevention)	INDICATOR C: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Protection)	INDICATOR D: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prosecution)
	INDICATOR E: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Provision of services)	INDICATOR F: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Partnerships)	INDICATOR G: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Policy)	

INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORKS

Institutional policy frameworks are enabling forces driving change on gender equality in RPOs and concern the overall organisation and structure of all measures and activities aimed at, or which might have positive effects on the ambition of, ending gender-based violence. An institutional policy framework usually involves several areas, academic leaders on different levels, and various stakeholders both within and outside the institution, together claiming a central strategy or overarching system for managing the institutional mechanisms to fight gender-based violence. Thus, an institutional framework goes beyond a single policy addressing gender-based violence, as the former often includes short- and long-term organisational aims and measures; long-term decisions for resource allocation and financial support; well-integrated ideas and concrete measures on, for example, developing safe educational and working conditions for students and staff; and measures for cultural change, especially on transforming norms in risk of conflicting with the safety of students and staff. See Table 2 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Table 2: ID1 Institutional framework for addressing gender-based violence

Institutional framework for addressing gender-based violence					
INDICATOR A: Institutional framework for addressing GBV					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integration</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
Policies, responsible management roles, experts on GBV, a budget frame, and other necessary measures for cultural change are not in place	Policies, responsible management roles, experts on GBV, a budget frame, or other necessary measures for cultural change are planned or upcoming, in their own right or as part of a wider framework	A framework including policies, responsible management roles, experts on addressing GBV, a budget frame, or other necessary measures (as part of a framework) for cultural change is in place but not yet fully functional	A framework including policies, responsible management roles, experts on addressing GBV, a budget frame, and other necessary measures for cultural change started to function with resources and responsibilities allocated	There are clear resources and responsibilities in place and the framework (including policies, management roles etc) are systematically used at all levels in the institution, with an allocated budget	Resources and responsibilities are in place, supported by an allocated budget, systematically at all levels, and there is ongoing monitoring and evaluation of GBV policies and measures informing institutional programmes and processes

CONCEPTS

Concepts, the coverage and definitions of the forms of gender-based violence and intersectionality, includes the understanding of gender-based violence, both in terms of the inclusion of multiple forms and inequalities (intersectionality). As argued in the UniSAFE theoretical and conceptual framework (Strid et al. 2021, p. 13), gender-based violence needs to be understood as a manifestation of gendered power inequalities within different forms, as captured in the following definition:

All forms of gender-based violence, violations and, abuse, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment – in both online and offline contexts, including emerging forms of violence, experienced as violence, violations and abuse not yet necessarily named or recognised as violence.

This definition goes beyond the current and previous scope and praxis in national legislation and policy in a majority of MS and AC, as well as the current state of institutional policies in a majority of RPOs and the policy framework set by the EC⁴. Naming and addressing multiple forms of discrimination, or framing challenges in terms of gendered inequalities, is an important step towards conceptualising gender-based violence further. Gendered inequalities are at the core of the concept of gender-based violence, both as a determinant and consequence of violence and abuse. Placing gendered inequalities at the core of gender-based violence opens for an **intersectional** perspective, i.e., the interconnected, complex ways in which multiple inequalities (age, sex, gender, race/ethnicity, disabilities, nationality, location, religion, sexual orientation, etc.) position people and enable violence and abuse. Intersectionality defined this way is an important and major shift in focus and understanding of the multiple, differentiated ways inequalities coexist and play out in gender-based violence experiences, as gender-based violence emanates from structural oppression. Intersectionality makes it more relevant and possible to both acknowledge different potentially vulnerable or minoritised groups and their specific intersectional experiences, needs, and demands and to pursue relevant structural transformative measures for the benefit and safety of all students and staff. See Table 3 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

⁴ For example, the EU (2020) strategy for gender equality 2020-2025. The recent Ljubljana Declaration (2021) and the Prague call for action (2022) illustrate important developments approaching this core definition.

Table 3: ID2 Concepts: coverage and definitions of the forms of gender-based violence and their intersections

INDICATOR A: Coverage and definitions of the forms of gender-based violence					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
No forms of GBV are mentioned nor defined in existing policies and measures	Some forms of GBV are mentioned in existing policies and measures, in a superficial manner, without explicit definitions, and not necessarily considering how violence is gendered or part of a continuum	Some forms of GBV are defined in existing policies and measures, but mostly cover harassment and bullying, without considering how violence is gendered or part of a continuum	Several forms of GBV are defined in existing policies and measures, including starting to consider how violence is gendered and part of a continuum	Several forms of GBV are defined in policies and measures and definitions consider how violence is gendered or part of a continuum	A broad range of forms of GBV is defined and there is an explicit understanding that they are related and part of a continuum. The definitions reflect the gender power relations within institutions
INDICATOR B: Intersectionality					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
Neither intersectional perspective nor how different grounds of inequalities might exacerbate sex/gender inequalities in relation to GBV are present in existing policies and measures	The experiences of GBV across different grounds of inequalities start to be considered in existing policies and measures, but in a superficial way; inequality groups may be mentioned.	The experiences of GBV across different grounds of inequalities are considered, but are treated individually, and how intersections of different grounds of inequalities can increase the prevalence and consequences of GBV is not considered in existing policies and measures	The experiences of GBV across different grounds of inequalities are considered, and are treated together, as well as how the intersectional effects of different grounds of inequalities can increase the prevalence and consequences of gender violence is considered in existing policies and measures	An intersectional perspective, i.e., the extent to which experiences at the intersections of different identities might create different experiences beyond just the combination of these identities, and/or beyond the gender binary, and is integrated in some existing policies and measures	An intersectional perspective is integrated in all relevant institutional policies and measures, with an understanding of intersectionality as structural power relations rather than the effects of individual inequalities, and is systematically integrated in all relevant existing policies and measures

VICTIM-CENTRED APPROACH

It is important to recognise and advocate a survivor-centred and trauma-informed approach, through an intersectional lens, when developing the content and logic of primary, secondary, and tertiary measures targeting gender-based violence. In other words, to inhibit (primary), deal with (secondary) and soften (tertiary) the consequences of experiences of violations and abuse (Salter & Gore 2020; WHO 2010).

Survivors’ naming, giving voice to, and in other ways sharing their experiences of violence and abuse must be heard, listened to, and acknowledged fully in a safe environment and guided by expert knowledge and experience. It is also important for institutions to develop processes whereby these experiences are made visible and documented, by using ethical protocols, and analysed in depth by experts, and finally transformed into concrete knowledge for targeted measures throughout the 7P model. In this process, past experiences of abuse and (potential risks of) re-traumatisation, indications of abusive study and workplace cultures and other potential risks and vulnerabilities need to inform and be considered through a victim centred approach in design, implementation and evaluation of measures and policies. Consequently, a victim-centred approach to addressing gender-based violence considers and takes into account the experiences and knowledge from victims and potential victims to inform measures addressing gender-based violence. See Table 4 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Table 4: ID3 Victim-centred approach for addressing gender-based violence

INDICATOR A: Victim-centred approach for addressing gender-based violence					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
The institution is unaware of the experiences and needs of victims of GBV	The institution starts to become aware of the experiences and needs of victims	Victims’ experiences and needs are considered in some measures and policies, but inconsistently	Victims’ experiences and needs are addressed in some measures and policies more consistently	Victims’ experiences and needs are at the centre of measures and policies, and are consistently and systematically addressed	All policies and measures addressing GBV are consistently and systematically victim centred in their design, implementation and evaluation

KNOWLEDGE AND EXPERTISE

The adequacy and effectiveness of an institution's approach to addressing gender-based violence will depend on the existing knowledge and expertise, and the willingness and capacity to use it. Knowledge and expertise, and their uptake, are key aspects of promoting institutional change and will have to be organised, sustained, and developed continuously as part of ongoing institutional processes.

Expert competencies cover a broad range of expertise (on gender, gender-based violence, intersectionality, gender mainstreaming, discrimination, etc) and expertise represented by different professions (educators, psychologists, administrators, researchers, etc.) from several strands of knowledge (practical, clinical, therapeutical, administrative, scientific) on gender-based violence, intersectionality, RPOs and academic cultures, and change management. Ensuring adequate time, resources, and skills among all those involved in investigating cases of gender-based violence, persons in relevant support functions, managers on different levels, union representatives, other involved stakeholders, and many others is crucial.

The organisation and development of capacity-building initiatives requires expert knowledge and skills and dedicated and competent professionals with an established mandate to manage, develop and deliver targeted activities. Capacity-building initiatives, as defined in this context, mainly concern introduction, training, education, supervision, mentoring, mutual learning activities (and other forms of sharing knowledge) on addressing gender-based violence for different target groups. Capacity-building ideally targets all students and staff, albeit it is often challenging to ensure participation of potential bystanders and perpetrators, specific target and vulnerable groups, and other relevant actors and stakeholders. Therefore, the use of targeted, tailored training initiatives is crucial for target groups, just as compulsory introductory, awareness-raising initiatives might be necessary, to ensure a common ground and understanding of gender-based violence throughout the institution. See Table 5 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Table 5: ID4 Knowledge and internal expertise on gender-based violence

INDICATOR A: Knowledge and internal expertise on gender-based violence					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
GBV knowledge and expertise are not available	GBV knowledge is insufficiently reflected in the design of actions; internal expertise is not acknowledged	GBV knowledge has been considered sometimes, and internal expertise is employed on an ad-hoc basis	GBV knowledge is considered, and internal expertise is used more consistently in the design, implementation or evaluation of measures and policies	GBV knowledge and expertise are consistently and systematically considered in the design, implementation and evaluation of measures and policies	The use of GBV knowledge and expertise is structurally embedded in the design, implementation and evaluation of measures and policies
INDICATOR B: Capacity-building initiatives on addressing gender-based violence					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
There is no capacity-building for GBV (although there may be some awareness-raising efforts)	Capacity-building initiatives that focus on GBV issues hardly exist and with no clear purpose	Capacity-building initiatives that focus on GBV exist on an ad-hoc basis according to the needs (i.e., limited to staff with a gender mandate)	GBV capacity-building initiatives are conducted more consistently according to the needs	Needs-oriented GBV capacity-building initiatives are systematically and regularly conducted, for both students and staff	GBV capacity-building initiatives are conducted on a systematic basis for defined groups of both students and staff at all levels, and their effectiveness is assessed
INDICATOR C: Provision of support materials for gender-based violence related work (guidelines, toolkits, directory of resources etc.)					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
No provision of support materials (guidelines, toolkits, reviews, etc)	The need to compile, adapt or develop support materials has been identified, but has not started	Support materials start to be compiled or developed	Support materials are available, for a basic range of measures	Support materials are in place, cover a broader range of types of measures, for both staff and students, and kept up to date through continuous development	Support materials cover a broad range of types of measures for both staff and students, and kept up to date and their effectiveness is assessed

LEADERSHIP COMMITMENT

Academic leaders, both in line and collegial management positions, are key actors for fostering organisational change, ensuring sound working conditions, and setting and maintaining ethical perspectives on social interactions in academic cultures. Research argues clearly on the importance of academic leaders' proactive engagement in addressing gender-based violence throughout the institution. Their skills and use of measures, and their proactive stance on creating inclusive academic cultures, are vital for addressing gender-based violence in RPOs (Lee 2018; Settles et al. 2006). Engagement in proactive measures against gender-based violence, at all levels of management in an institution, does not come easy or by itself. It is also often temporary, arbitrary to some extent, and sometimes due to personal characteristics among top or senior management individuals. Leadership engagement ranges from a complete lack of expression of interests to address gender-based violence to an explicit commitment to addressing gender-based violence in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, connected to a vision and strategy that are expressed in institutional policy documents, and operationalised in an action plan. See Table 6 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Table 6: ID5 Leadership commitment to addressing gender-based violence

INDICATOR A: Leadership commitment to addressing gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
Leaders do not express any interest or commitment to addressing GBV	One or a few individual leaders express commitment to addressing GBV occasionally and informally	Commitment to addressing GBV starts to feature more clearly in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, but this reflects a superficial commitment of the institution	Commitment to addressing GBV is explicit in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, and work has started towards reflecting this commitment in institutional policy documents	Commitment to addressing GBV is explicit in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, and is connected to a vision and strategy that are expressed in institutional policy documents	Commitment to addressing GBV is explicit in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, is connected to a vision and strategy that are expressed in institutional policy documents, and operationalised in an action plan

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION

It is paramount to ensure access to knowledge on all aspects of the institutional policy framework against gender-based violence: targeted measures, resources and support material, data on prevalence, services and support, contact persons, etc. This requires asserting relevant information is available (functional, in several languages, etc), useful (in line with target groups’ knowledge, skills and needs) and up-to-date (revised and continuously developed in line with research and praxis) for all target groups, and using all relevant online and offline communication platforms. This is a challenging task for institutions as it has to be organised in a sustained way and will depend on adequate resource allocation, knowledge and skills, and long-term engagement. A lack of adequate information, even on minor aspects, can be decisive for those willing to formally report an incident or to seek relevant support. It is also of relevance to whether engagement in work and student groups is progressing, and to what extent bystander intervention will take place or not. Then there is a continuous need for assuring *internal transparency* about different resources, data on prevalence, support services, and other aspects. Likewise, *external communication* is important for several reasons: addressing prospective students and staff on the work done on inclusive academic cultures, informing expanded target groups outside of internal communication channels on support services. See Table 7 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Table 7: ID6 Internal transparency of policies, data on prevalence, measures, knowledge, and support structures

INDICATOR A: Internal transparency of policies, data on prevalence, measures, knowledge, and support structures					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
There is no communication nor information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, or support structures internally	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists, but is not communicated	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists and is communicated on an ad hoc basis	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists and is communicated regularly internally, but inconsistently across staff and students, and faculties/departments	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists, and is systematically and actively communicated internally where relevant	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students is continuously reviewed, revised and kept up to date, within a clear communication strategy on GBV

INDICATOR B: External transparency of policies, data on prevalence, measures, knowledge, and support structures					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
There is no communication nor information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures or support structures externally	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or other relevant aspects exist but are not communicated to external stakeholders	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or other relevant aspects is made available upon request to external stakeholders	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or other relevant aspects is communicated to external stakeholders, but inconsistent	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and other relevant aspects is systematically and actively communicated and made available to external stakeholders where relevant	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge, and other relevant aspects to all external stakeholders is continuously reviewed, revised and kept up to date, within a clear communication strategy on GBV

MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The final impact driver in the assessment framework concerns the importance of systematic monitoring and evaluation of progress in addressing gender-based violence within the institution. Indicators on the prevalence of gender-based violence in the EU more generally, based on the Istanbul Convention (CoE 2011) as well as on other legal and policy frameworks (ILO 2019; UNHCR 2020), are continuously reframed by different stakeholders. However, monitoring of gender-based violence in RPOs is still lacking (Strid et al. 2021; Huck et al. 2022).

Institutional gender-based violence monitoring and evaluation efforts consist of several different measures, incentives and the production and use of relevant data and documentation. A starting point is to establish and document to what extent there are available data on all aspects of the 7P model. Further, a sustained, institutional process is needed for monitoring the effectiveness of the various components of the institutional framework on addressing gender-based violence. This includes, for example, measuring and documenting the relevance and effects of case management procedures, information, and training, as well as support service activities. Finally, the monitoring and evaluation system must ensure data and documentation are used for analysis, adjustment of measures if needed, and development of future initiatives. This latter step in a monitoring and

evaluation cycle is crucial for the understanding of strengths and weaknesses to address in future work. See Table 8 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Table 8: ID7 Existence of structures or other incentives for monitoring and evaluation of measures to address gender-based violence

INDICATOR A: Existence of structures or other incentives for monitoring and evaluation of measures to address gender-based violence					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integrated</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
No structures, schemes, devices, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/ or evaluating measures to address GBV are in place	Structures, schemes, devices, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are planned or upcoming	Structures, schemes, devices, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are starting to be implemented, but on an ad hoc basis	Structures, schemes, devices, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are in place and take place regularly, but with ad hoc provisions for resourcing	Structures, schemes, devices, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and evaluating all measures to address GBV, with systematic provision for resourcing	Monitoring and evaluation of all policies and measures to address GBV are structurally foreseen and resourced, and inform the development and implementation of both existing and new measures

INSTITUTIONAL MEASURES: COVERAGE AND USE OF THE 7P MODEL

The 7P model covers all relevant policies and measures for addressing gender-based violence in RPOs.⁵ The 7P model is an extended and revised framework for measures combining and going beyond the UN 3P approach (Prevention, Protection, Prosecution) (UN 2017) and the Council of Europe 4P approach (Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Policies) (CoE 2011) outlined in the Istanbul Convention and includes a wider range and more clearly defined set of measures to address gender-based violence (Anitha & Lewis et al. 2019) (see Text Box 1 below for the definition of each P). See Table 8 for the operationalisation of this impact driver.

Text box 1: The 7P model⁶

POLICY	Policy is the basis of the approach and refers to both a coherent set of measures with a clear vision and strategy, and specific policy documents detailing such measures.
PREVALENCE	Prevalence and incidence estimates contribute to evidence-based policymaking. Data can be collected through surveys or administrative processes (e.g. the registration of complaints). Importantly, data collection and analysis must take an intersectional approach, taking into account, for example, people's ethnicity and origin, gender identity, sexual orientation, as well as their function within the organisation.
PREVENTION	Prevention refers to measures that promote changes in social and cultural behaviour. This may include induction materials for both staff and students; internal and external publicity and training; public statements and visuals.
PROTECTION	Protection is about ensuring safety and meeting the needs of (potential) victims and survivors, with the objective to avoid (further) harm to be inflicted. This includes clear processes, procedures, and infrastructure for reporting occurrences, and training for those responsible for handling cases. Protection may comprise measures such as a restraining order; offering a change of dormitory, student group, unit or supervisor.
PROSECUTION	Prosecution and disciplinary measures cover legal and disciplinary proceedings against perpetrators, and related investigative measures and judicial proceedings. This includes possible warnings, suspension, termination of employment and study, as legally appropriate, and liaison with legal, police and criminal justice organisations and professionals.
PROVISION OF SERVICES	Provision of services refers to the services offered to support victims, families, bystanders, perpetrators and the community affected by gender-based violence. It can include counselling; legal, psychological and medical support; accommodating different exam, study or teaching schedules; but also rehabilitation programmes for perpetrators. Importantly, the availability of services needs to be well known to all staff and students as well as to managers and supervisors.
PARTNERSHIPS	Partnerships relate to the involvement of relevant actors at all levels, such as governmental agencies, civil society organisations, trade unions, or staff and student associations.

⁵ The 7P model was originally developed by Lut Mergaert and colleagues, see Mergaert et al 2016.

⁶ Text box taken from Mergaert et al. 2023 Working paper, in turn developed from Mergaert et al. 2016, Strid et al. 2021 and insights from workshops conducted in UniSAFE WP7.

Table 8: ID8 Institutional measures: comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model

INDICATOR A: Prevalence					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integration</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
No data collection is in place (survey or administrative)	A survey or administrative data collection/collation on the prevalence of GBV is planned or upcoming	Data on the prevalence of GBV has been collected, but this was a one-off data collection	Data on the prevalence of GBV is collected regularly either from administrative sources or a survey	Data is collected and analysed on a regular, annual basis from both administrative data and surveys	Ongoing data analysis (from surveys and administrative sources) is feeding into institutional policies and practices
INDICATOR B: Prevention					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integration</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
No measures or activities to promote change in behaviour or attitudes on GBV among staff or students are in place	Some measures or activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes on GBV among staff or students are planned or upcoming	Measures or activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes on GBV have started, but they only target either staff or students	Measures and activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes on GBV have been implemented targeting both staff and students	Measures and activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes on GBV among staff and students are starting to be systematically included in the institutional activities	Measures and activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes on GBV among staff and students are available at all organisational levels, including monitoring and evaluation.
INDICATOR C: Protection					
<i>Starting point</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>Inception</i>	<i>Growth</i>	<i>Integration</i>	<i>Institutionalisation</i>
No awareness nor knowledge of actions and measures on GBV to ensure the safety of (potential) victims is in place	The institution starts to become aware of the need to offer protective measures to victims.	Some actions and measures to protect victims of GBV can be implemented upon request	Actions and measures to ensure the safety of (potential) victims of GBV are sometimes offered; there is knowledge of the available actions and measures	Actions and measures to ensure the safety of (potential) victims are available without request and are systematically considered.	There is an established repertoire of protective actions and measures in place that is reviewed for the purpose of institutional learning on a regular basis

INDICATOR D: Prosecution					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No procedures covering investigation, disciplinary measures or knowledge of legal proceedings exist.	Procedures are discussed on implementing disciplinary measures or legal proceedings	Procedures have started to be implemented, but they are incomplete, and their formalisation is inconsistent	Procedures covering investigation, disciplinary measures and legal proceedings are in place (on paper) and cover both staff and students, but implementation is inconsistent.	Procedures are robust, comprehensive and coherent, and systematically and consistently implemented across the institution	Procedures are well established, widely known and transparent, and their effectiveness is regularly reviewed
INDICATOR E: Provision of services					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No services are provided	Services to victims are planned or upcoming	Some services, specifically equipped to deal with GBV, are available and predominately focused on victims	Services specifically equipped to deal with GBV are available for several groups (victims, family, offenders, perpetrators, and bystanders) and the organisation is working on professionalising its service offer (in terms of quality, coordination, accessibility)	Services to victims, family, offenders, perpetrators and bystanders etc and the wider community (of the case) are systematically and consistently implemented across the institution and resources to improve and sustain? them are available	Services to victims, family, offenders, perpetrators, and bystanders etc and the wider community (of the case) are well established, widely known, and transparent, and their effectiveness is regularly reviewed

INDICATOR F: Partnerships					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No involvement of relevant actors working in collaboration on GBV	Collaboration with relevant actors on GBV is planned or upcoming	Involvement of relevant actors in collaborative actions on GBV has started	Involvement of relevant actors in collaborative actions on GBV is starting to shape internal measures and activities	Involvement of relevant actors is systematically and consistently considered in the development and implementation of internal measures in the institution	Systematic involvement of relevant actors is integral to the development and implementation of internal measures in the institution
INDICATOR G: Policy					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
There are no policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV, nor any budget to support institutional measures	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV are planned or upcoming, as a stand-alone area or included in other policy areas, but there is no budget allocated	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV have been introduced, but there is no clear vision nor strategy of yet, but they are not they fully functional, and there is no budget allocated	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV are in place, started to function and are supported by allocated resources and responsibilities	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV frame a coherent set of measures with a clear vision, as well as a comprehensive strategy that responds to the problems of GBV	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV and frame a coherent set of measures with a clear vision, as well as comprehensive strategy that responds to the problems of GBV, are included in a GEP, and there is ongoing monitoring and evaluation of GBV policies and measures informing institutional programmes and processes

THE ASSESSMENT TOOL⁷

The next step will be to develop the framework into a concrete tool to be used by RPOs, similar to the CASPER Tool. The Impact Drivers model presented in the tool comprise the eight impact drivers for addressing gender-based violence for research and higher education institution. For each of the impact drivers, the indicators have been identified in this assessment framework. The model of six stages allows to synthesise the results of the analysis, as well as to situate the institution in relation to/compared to other institutions addressing gender-based violence.

A grid will be prepared to allow identifying the stage of institutionalisation for each impact driver, using rubrics. Rubrics are “tools that help to formalise processes of evaluation or assessment by outlining agreed upon criteria that mark different levels of performance. Rubrics can be tailored to meet context-specific needs rather than referring to seemingly ‘objective’ outside criteria, i.e., type and degree of change between the different criteria can be chosen on a case-by-case basis.” (UNIFEM, 2010:45).

The model incorporates the understanding that institutional capacity is a dynamic reality, evolving over time and influenced by various factors (European Commission, 2007). By assessing institutional capacity per impact driver, a refined insight into particular strengths and weaknesses of the institution’s capacity to address gender-based violence is obtained.

HOW TO USE THE TOOL

The self-assessment tool will be constructed in MS Excel. It consists of four sheets:

1. The first sheet constitutes the self-completion checklist.
2. The second sheet provides the list of the Impact Drivers, each with their proposed indicators. This sheet also provides clarifications for some items that might require an explanation.
3. The third sheet is automatically completed, based on the assessments made in the first sheet. It presents the results of the institutions, in terms of its capacity for addressing gender-based violence in the form of a table and two charts (one bar chart and one radar graph).
4. The fourth sheet is a technical sheet that contains the answer options for the drop-down answer boxes on sheet 1 and is not to be modified by the users.

The first sheet, the self-completion checklist, is to be completed by the institution. Institutions are invited to indicate the level of institutionalisation for each impact driver. For this purpose, a dropdown list with six answer options is provided in column B, corresponding to: 0=starting point, 1=project, 2=inception, 3=growth, 4=integration, 5=institutionalisation. To determine the level of institutionalisation per impact driver, levels for each indicator are

⁷ This guidance is based on the guidelines for the impact driver model developed in the EU funded CASPER (GA: 872113) under Task 5.6 – Exploration and first development of an operational tool to assess sustainable institutional change, see Mergaert et al. (2022).

identified by the rubrics (in columns E to J). For each of the indicators, its level of institutionalisation is marked in column L. Together, these help to decide which level to assign to the impact driver. Note that column L is not mandatory for this exercise, but recommended as it makes the exercise more transparent and will allow for a better understanding of the assessment later on when revisiting the tool.

A brief justification or explanation of each given rating is requested in column M. While such justification is not mandatory, it is again recommended because these explanations will help institutions understand their earlier assessment when referred to it later on. The self-assessment tool can serve to monitor the progress that is made in the institution towards building institutional capacity for eradicating gender-based violence.

Lastly, in column N, it is requested to indicate which 'evidence' or proof can be provided to justify the rating. Completing it will allow a better test use of the tool and for a better insight into how the institution has progressed when the exercise is repeated.

Comments or reflections in relation to interpretation or scoring can be added in column O.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The assessment framework aims to capture the progress made by institutions in addressing gender-based violence, along six progressive stages:

Starting point > Project > Inception > Growth > Integration > Institutionalisation

Each stage builds upon the preceding one, with the assumption that an institution will progressively develop from one stage to the next. The first stage of 'Starting point' represents point zero, where nothing is in place yet. The last stage, that of 'institutionalisation' represents the aspirational goal towards which institutions can work in their efforts to address gender-based violence.

Each stage is attributed a score, ranging from 0 to 5, for each of the indicators. An aggregate score can then be computed to provide a more holistic assessment. This scoring system allows RPOs to identify their current position, and what to put in place going forward for addressing gender-based violence more effectively. The aim of the assessment framework is therefore dual: the scores can provide a summative assessment of where the institution currently stands, but also a formative assessment to suggest how to develop institutional policies and measures further. The process can be repeated at regular intervals to assess progress.

The score for each impact driver can be obtained through averaging scores from its indicators (i.e. the sum derived from assessment criteria value(s) for its indicators, divided by the number of indicators assessed). In cases where there is only one indicator, the impact driver score is then the same as the score attributed to this indicator.

The results can be visualised on a radar chart, outline the progress made across each of the impact drivers for the overall model (Figure 1: Radar chart for assessing progress along Impact Drivers 1-8). In addition, the results of the assessment that are specifically related to the 7P model can be visualised in a dedicated radar chart (Figure 2: Radar chart for assessing progress along the 7P model).

Figure 1: Radar chart for assessing progress along Impact Drivers 1-8

Figure 2: Radar chart for assessing progress along the 7P model

ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

OVERVIEW

Impact drivers	Indicators						
ID1: Institutional framework	INDICATOR A: Institutional framework for addressing GBV						
ID2: Concepts Coverage and knowledge of the forms of GBV and their intersections	INDICATOR A: Concepts and definitions of GBV	INDICATOR B: Intersectionality					
ID3: Institutional measures (Coverage and use of the 7P model)	INDICATOR A: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prevalence)	INDICATOR B: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prevention)	INDICATOR C: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Protection)	INDICATOR D: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prosecution)	INDICATOR E: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Provision of services)	INDICATOR F: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Partnerships)	INDICATOR G: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Policies)
ID4: Victim-centred approach Consideration of experiences and knowledge from survivors, bystanders,	INDICATOR A: Victim-centred approach						

perpetrators, and at-risk groups to inform measures addressing GBV							
ID5: Knowledge and expertise Available competencies, capacity-building initiatives, and support material	INDICATOR A: Availability and use of Internal knowledge and expertise	INDICATOR B: Capacity-building initiatives on addressing GBV	INDICATOR C: Availability and use of support material for awareness-raising and capacity-building				
ID6: Leadership commitment	INDICATOR A: Leadership commitment						
ID7: Internal and external transparency of information and communication	INDICATOR A: Internal transparency of policy, data, measures, knowledge, and support structures	INDICATOR B: External transparency of policy, data, measures, knowledge, and support structures					

<p>ID8: Monitoring and evaluation</p>	<p>INDICATOR A: Existence of structures or other incentives for monitoring and evaluation of measures to address GBV</p>						
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IMPACT DRIVERS WITH INDICATORS AND RUBRICS

IMPACT DRIVER 1		Institutional framework for addressing gender-based violence			
INDICATOR A: Institutional framework for addressing gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
Policies, responsible management roles, experts on GBV, a budget frame, and other necessary measures for cultural change are not in place	Policies, responsible management roles, experts on GBV, a budget frame, or other necessary measures for cultural change are planned or upcoming, in their own right or as part of a wider framework	A framework including policies, responsible management roles, experts on addressing GBV, a budget line, or other necessary measures (as part of a framework) for cultural change is in place but not yet fully functional	A framework including policies, responsible management roles, experts on addressing GBV, a budget frame, and other necessary measures for cultural change started to function with resources and responsibilities allocated	There are clear resources and responsibilities in place and the framework (including policies, management roles etc) are systematically used at all levels in the institution, with an allocated budget	Resources and responsibilities are in place, supported by an allocated budget, systematically at all levels, and there is ongoing monitoring and evaluation of GBV policies and measures informing institutional programmes and processes

IMPACT DRIVER 2		Concepts: Coverage and definitions of the forms of gender-based violence and their intersections			
INDICATOR A: Coverage and definitions of the forms of gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No forms of GBV are mentioned nor defined in existing policies and measures	Some forms of GBV are mentioned in existing policies and measures, in a superficial manner, without explicit definitions, and not necessarily considering how violence is gendered or part of a continuum	Some forms of GBV are defined in existing policies and measures, but mostly cover harassment and bullying, without considering how violence is gendered or part of a continuum	Several forms of GBV are defined in existing policies and measures, including starting to consider how violence is gendered and part of a continuum	Several forms of GBV are defined in existing policies and measures, and definitions consider how violence is gendered and part of a continuum	A broad range of forms of GBV is defined and there is an explicit understanding that they are related and part of a continuum. The definitions reflect the gender power relations within institutions
INDICATOR B: Intersectionality					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
Neither intersectional perspective nor how	The experiences of GBV across different grounds	The experiences of GBV across different grounds	The experiences of GBV across different grounds	An intersectional perspective, i.e., the	An intersectional perspective is integrated

different grounds of inequalities might exacerbate sex/gender inequalities in relation to GBV are present in existing policies and measures	of inequalities start to be considered in existing policies and measures, but in a superficial way; inequality groups may be mentioned.	of inequalities are considered, but are treated individually, and how intersections of different grounds of inequalities can increase the prevalence and consequences of GBV is not considered in existing policies and measures	of inequalities are considered, and are treated together, as well as how the intersectional effects of different grounds of inequalities can increase the prevalence and consequences of gender violence is considered in existing policies and measures	extent to which experiences at the intersections of different identities might create different experiences beyond just the combination of these identities, and/or beyond the gender binary, is integrated in some existing policies and measures	in all relevant institutional policies and measures, with an understanding of intersectionality as structural power relations rather than the effects of individual inequalities, and is systematically integrated in all relevant existing policies and measures
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IMPACT DRIVER 3		Victim-centred approach for addressing gender-based violence			
INDICATOR A: Victim-centred approach for addressing gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
The institution is unaware of the experiences and needs of victims of GBV	the institution starts to become aware of the experiences and needs of victims	Victims' experiences and needs are considered in some measures and policies, but inconsistently	Victims' experiences and needs are addressed in some measures and policies more consistently	Victims' experiences and needs are at the centre of measures and policies, and are consistently and systematically addressed	All policies and measures addressing GBV are consistently and systematically victim centred in their design, implementation and evaluation

IMPACT DRIVER 4		Available competencies, capacity-building initiatives, and support material			
INDICATOR A: Knowledge and internal expertise on gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
GBV knowledge and expertise are not available	GBV knowledge is insufficiently reflected in the design of actions; internal expertise is not acknowledged	GBV knowledge has been considered sometimes, and internal expertise is employed on an ad-hoc basis	GBV knowledge is considered, and internal expertise is used more consistently in the design, implementation or evaluation of measures and policies	GBV knowledge and expertise are consistently and systematically considered in the design, implementation and evaluation of measures and policies	The use of GBV knowledge and expertise is structurally embedded in the design, implementation and evaluation of measures and policies
INDICATOR B: Capacity-building initiatives on addressing gender-based violence					

Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
There is no capacity-building for GBV (although there may be some awareness-raising efforts)	Capacity-building initiatives that focus on GBV issues hardly exist and with no clear purpose	Capacity-building initiatives that focus on GBV exist on an ad-hoc basis according to the needs (i.e., limited to staff with a gender mandate)	GBV capacity-building initiatives are conducted more consistently according to the needs	Needs-oriented GBV capacity-building initiatives are systematically and regularly conducted, for both students and staff	GBV capacity-building initiatives are conducted on a systematic basis for defined groups of both students and staff at all levels, and their effectiveness is assessed
INDICATOR C: Provision of support materials for gender-based violence related work (guidelines, toolkits, directory of resources etc.)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
No provision of support materials (guidelines, toolkits, reviews, etc) d	The need to compile, adapt or develop support materials has been identified, but has not started	Support materials start to be compiled or developed	Support materials are available, for a basic range of measures	Support materials are in place, cover a broader range of types of measures, for both staff and students, and kept up to date through continuous development	Support materials cover a broad range of types of measures for both staff and students, and kept up to date and their effectiveness is assessed

Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
IMPACT DRIVER 5 Leadership commitment to addressing gender-based violence					
INDICATOR A: Leadership commitment to addressing gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
Leaders do not express any interest or commitment to addressing GBV	One or a few individual leaders express commitment to addressing GBV occasionally and informally	A commitment to addressing GBV starts to feature more clearly in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, but this reflects a superficial commitment of the institution	A commitment to addressing GBV is explicit in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, and work has started towards reflecting this commitment in institutional policy documents	A commitment to addressing GBV is explicit in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, and is connected to a vision and strategy that are expressed in institutional policy documents	A commitment to addressing GBV is explicit in the public discourse and internal communications of the leaders, is connected to a vision and strategy that are expressed in institutional policy documents, and operationalised in an action plan

IMPACT DRIVER 6		Internal and external transparency of policies, data on prevalence, measures, knowledge, and support structures			
INDICATOR A: Internal transparency of policies, data on prevalence, measures, knowledge, and support structures					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
There is no communication nor information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, or support structures internally	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists, but is not communicated	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists and is communicated on an ad hoc basis	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists and is communicated regularly internally, but inconsistently across staff and students, and faculties/departments	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students exists, and is systematically and actively communicated internally where relevant	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or available support to staff and students is continuously reviewed, revised and kept up to date, within a clear internal communication strategy on GBV
INDICATOR B: External transparency of policies, data on prevalence, measures, knowledge, and support structures					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
There is no communication nor information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures or support structures externally	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or other relevant aspects exist but are not communicated to external stakeholders	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or other relevant aspects is made available upon request to external stakeholders	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and/or other relevant aspects is communicated to external stakeholders, but inconsistent	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge and other relevant aspects is systematically and actively communicated and made available to external stakeholders where relevant	Information on policies, data on prevalence, existing measures, knowledge, and other relevant aspects to all external stakeholders is continuously reviewed, revised and kept up to date, within a clear external communication strategy on GBV

IMPACT DRIVER 7	Existence of structures or other incentives for monitoring and evaluation of measures to address gender-based violence				
INDICATOR A: Existence of structures or other incentives for monitoring and evaluation of measures to address gender-based violence					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integrated	Institutionalisation
No structures, schemes, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are in place	Structures, schemes, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are planned or upcoming	Structures, schemes, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are starting to be implemented, but on an ad hoc basis	Structures, schemes, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and/or evaluating measures to address GBV are in place and implemented regularly, but with ad hoc provisions for resourcing	Structures, schemes, resources, or targeted efforts for monitoring and evaluating all measures to address GBV are implemented regularly and with systematic provisions for resourcing/resourced through an institutional budget	Monitoring and evaluation of all policies and measures to address GBV are structurally foreseen and resourced through regular institutional budget line, and inform the development and implementation of both existing and new measures

IMPACT DRIVER 8	Institutional measures (Coverage and use of the 7P model)				
INDICATOR A: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prevalence)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No data collection is in place (survey or administrative)	A survey or administrative data collection/collation on the prevalence of GBV is planned or upcoming	Data on the prevalence of GBV has been collected, but this was a one-off data collection	Data on the prevalence of GBV is collected regularly either from administrative sources or a survey	Data is collected and analysed on a regular, annual basis from both administrative data and surveys	Ongoing data analysis (from surveys and administrative sources) is feeding into institutional policies and practices
INDICATOR B: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prevention)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No measures or activities to promote change in behaviour or attitudes on	Some measures or activities to promote change in behaviour and	Measures or activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes	Measures and activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes	Measures and activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes	Measures and activities to promote change in behaviour and attitudes

GBV among staff or students are in place	attitudes on GBV among staff or students are planned or upcoming	on GBV have started, but they only target either staff or students	on GBV have been implemented targeting both staff and students	on GBV among staff and students are starting to be systematically included in the institutional activities	on GBV among staff and students are available at all organisational levels, including monitoring and evaluation.
INDICATOR C: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Protection)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No awareness nor knowledge of actions and measures on GBV to ensure the safety of (potential) victims is in place	The institution starts to become aware of the need to offer protective measures to victims.	Some actions and measures to protect victims of GBV can be implemented upon request	Actions and measures to ensure the safety of (potential) victims of GBV are sometimes offered; there is knowledge of the available actions and measures	Actions and measures to ensure the safety of (potential) victims are available without request and are systematically considered.	There is an established repertoire of protective actions and measures in place that is reviewed for the purpose of institutional learning on a regular basis
INDICATOR D: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Prosecution)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No procedures covering investigation, disciplinary measures or knowledge of legal proceedings exist.	Procedures are discussed on implementing disciplinary measures or legal proceedings	Procedures have started to be implemented, but they are incomplete, and their formalisation is inconsistent	Procedures covering investigation, disciplinary measures and legal proceedings are in place (on paper) and cover both staff and students, but implementation is inconsistent.	Procedures are robust, comprehensive and coherent, and systematically and consistently implemented across the institution	Procedures are well established, widely known and transparent, and their effectiveness is regularly reviewed
INDICATOR E: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Provision of services)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No services are provided	Services to victims are planned or upcoming	Some services, specifically equipped to deal with GBV, are available and predominately focused on victims	Services specifically equipped to deal with GBV are available for several groups (victims, family, offenders, perpetrators, and bystanders) and the organisation is working on professionalising its service offer (in terms of	Services to victims, family, offenders, perpetrators and bystanders etc and the wider community (of the case) are systematically and consistently implemented across the institution and resources to improve and sustain? them are available	Services to victims, family, offenders, perpetrators, and bystanders etc and the wider community (of the case) are well established, widely known, and transparent, and their effectiveness is regularly reviewed

			quality, coordination, accessibility)		
INDICATOR F: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Partnerships)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
No involvement of relevant actors working in collaboration on GBV	Collaboration with relevant actors on GBV is planned or upcoming	Involvement of relevant actors in collaborative actions on GBV has started	Involvement of relevant actors in collaborative actions on GBV is starting to shape internal measures and activities	Involvement of relevant actors is systematically and consistently considered in the development and implementation of internal measures in the institution	Systematic involvement of relevant actors is integral to the development and implementation of internal measures in the institution
INDICATOR G: Comprehensiveness and use of the 7P model (Policy)					
Starting point	Project	Inception	Growth	Integration	Institutionalisation
There are no policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV, nor any budget to support institutional measures	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV are planned or upcoming, as a stand-alone area or included in other policy areas, but there is no budget allocated	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV have been introduced, but there is no clear vision nor strategy of yet, but they are not they fully functional, and there is no budget allocated	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV are in place, started to function and are supported by allocated resources and responsibilities	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV frame a coherent set of measures with a clear vision, as well as a comprehensive strategy that responds to the problems of GBV	Policy documents which explicitly formalise the organisation's commitment to fight GBV and frame a coherent set of measures with a clear vision, as well as comprehensive strategy that responds to the problems of GBV, are included in a GEP, and there is ongoing monitoring and evaluation of GBV policies and measures informing institutional programmes and processes

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